
Digital Integration/Invasion in *Jatra*: A Critical Investigation in Bengal

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Abstract

The post-Independence Bengal saw a sea-change in its cultural panorama vis-à-vis *Jatra*. From the Sakti & Krishna *Jatra* to secular *Jatra*, from bamboo flute and *dhol* to modern orchestra and from the lyrical song to thundering melodrama, *Jatra* has undergone a radical transition along with the socio-political and cultural drift with time. It has ever been a major entertainment industry in rural Bengal and has greatly been influenced by the proscenium theatre. With the blazing lights, ticket systems and integrating digital means, *Jatra* has imbibed coinages e.g, Jatrscope, Cinerama, etc. over the time. In age of television and cinema, *Jatra* has introduced highly fashionable costumes, popular television artists, motor driven revolving cyclorama stage and retellings of stories of popular Bollywood and Tollywood movies. Various electronic media and gadgets have given this folk form a new paradigm in popular culture and imagination of rural Bengal. Media, music, liberalization and westernization influenced the popular rural socio-political and cultural behaviourism very profoundly. The present inquiry is a nuanced study of *Jatra* in the light of digitalization with its merits and demerits.

Keywords

Jatra, Digitalization, Popular Culture, Rural Bengal

Background

Jatra is the popular dramatic performance that has been prevalent in Bengal (including Bangladesh), Odisha and Assam for a long time. The word *Jatra* is derived from the word 'ya' - 'to go' Thus, *Jatra* means a 'cavalcade' or a 'procession' in the honour of the Gods or Goddesses. As the popular belief says the performative tradition originates in the Dionysian cult in the West, *Jatra* also originates in ceremonious ritual. Precisely, the usage of the term *Jatra* can be found in Bharata's *Natya Shastra* and Bhavabhuti's *Malati Madhava*. Before the particular form of dramatic representation came to exist at all, there were several popular performative traditions like *Kavi Gaan*, *Panchali*, *Kirtan*, *Kathakata*, etc. in rural Bengal growing independently along with the parallel development of the elite Sanskrit theatre in the medieval ages. In the late medieval age, *Jatra* grew out of the confluence of these popular performative genres. Perhaps, this is the reason why there is no general agreement on the origin of *Jatra*. Some scholars believe it to be a Vedic phenomenon, while some hold it as a performative tradition of the Puranic Age. Critic Kironmay Raha identifies *Jatra* to be originating as an associative ritual of religion. It evolved, like folk theatre in other parts of India, along distinctive lines and developed its distinctive features suited to the native genius of the regional people. The commonly accepted view is that the word had its origin in the ritualistic musical processions that formed part of the religious festivals in which the local deities were carried from one place to another.

In Bengal, *Jatra* as a distinct dramatic presentation had begun to take its shape with the worship of Shakti cult in *Chandi Jatra*. It dealt with the Great War between the demons and the Goddess Chandi. Later in the 16th century, when entire eastern India was swiped by the wave of Vaishnavism, a new kind of folk performance called *Krishna Jatra* became predominant in the popular imagination. It is said that Chaitanya Dev after returning from Gaya in 1506 played the role of Rukmini in *Rukmini Haran (The Abduction of Rukmini)* at the house of Chandra Sekhar. *Krishna Jatra* deals with the *Lila* (life and action) of Lord Krishna characterized by heroism, devotion, melodious songs and demonstration accompanied by folk music. The audience is mesmerized so much that every performance on Krishna's life came to be known as *Krishna Jatra* or popularly called as *Kesto Jatra*.

Fig. 1 Stage-plan for *Krishna Jatra*, with the spectators on the other side of the pond. (Source: Dr. Nirban Manna)

Towards the end of the Muslim rule, in the new form of amateur *Jatra* the divine love and devotion slowly yielded to secular themes dealing with human love and attraction and thereby beginning to lose its glory. Even *Kesto Jatra* was performed in a different style altogether. The amateur *Jatra* desecrated the performative cult as much as the colonial enterprise contributed towards the rapid decline of *Jatra* in the 18th & 19th century. When the British brought their capitalist mode of urban entertainment, namely 'Theatre', the once devotional *Jatra* suddenly became a low form of performance. And imported theatre, Shakespeare and the proscenium stage became the discourse of high culture. An Anglo-Indian journal named *Calcutta Review* (1851) narrated their impression about native theatrical amusement in the following words, which severely lacked empathy:

India in her high and palmy state had also had a dramatic literature of her own and scenic representations to gratify the people... We shall proceed to make a remark or two on the state of the drama as it now exists among the Bengalis. Of the representations called *jatras* we dare not give here a detailed description. They are wretched from the commencement to the Fifth Act. The plots are very often the amours of Krishna, or the love of Vidya and Sundar. In the representation of Krishna-*jatras*, boys arrayed in the habits of Sakhies and Gopinis (milk-maids) cut the principal figures on the stage. It would require the pencil of a master-painter to portray these fairies of the Bengali stage. The sooty complexion, their coal black cheeks, their haggard eyes, their long extended arms, their gaping mouths and their puerile attire excite disgust. Their external deformity is rivalled by their discordant voices, for the screechings of the night-owls, the howlings of the jackals and barking of the dogs that bay the moon are harmony itself compared with their horrid yells. Their dances are in strict accordance with the other accessories. In the evolutions of the hands and feet dignified with the name of dancing, they imitate all posture and gestures calculated to soil the mind and pollute the fancy. (Dasgupta, 136)

The British had aimed in the enterprise of cultural colonialism too. They created a class of mimic man or *Babu* and always wanted the 'native' to be distant from the popular culture, thereby uprooting people from their identity and strengthening their colonial enterprise. It can be said the British were quite successful in it. By the late 19th and early 20th century, the theme and stylization had changed so much that it could no longer be differentiated from the urban theatre. The modern *Jatra* in terms of secularization, stylization, and representation owed much to the popular *jatrawright* of 19th century Motilal Roy, a contemporary to Girish Ghosh.

During the last decades of the 19th century, Roy changed the old style of acting and costume and gave the rural mass a taste of theatre; thus, acting came out of devotional meekness and became stylized, demonstrative and expressive. He changed the old style of acting and costume and gave rural people a taste of grandeur in performance. Roy tried to bridge the gaps between an actor's internal realization of emotion and stage representation of it, so he advocated emotionally charged performance in his mythical operas like *Kaliyadaman*, *Vastra Haran* and *Brajalila*. In spite of the attempts to merge rural dramatic performance with the imported urban theatre, there were several distinguished affairs like the use of *jurigaan*, instruments, song to change the scene, thundering acting, stock

characters (Vivek, Narad, Niyati, etc.) which established *Jatra* as a distinct dramatic presentation by its own.

During this time *Jatra* received heavy criticism of being lewd, low and insipid among the so-called guardians of the high culture. Some people called *Jatra* as ‘*apaya*’ or ‘inauspicious’ (in place of *Opera* in sarcastic malapropism). Pandit Ram Narayan Tarkaratna, during the composition of *Ratnaboli* (1857), remarked: “Everyone who has been acquainted with the incomparable beauty and wealth of English and Sanskrit Dramas, has grown disgusted with despicable *Jatras*” (Dasgupta 135). Ultimately *Jatra* succumbed before this colonial discourse of high and low culture. The rapid growth of urban culture and taste had appropriated and expropriated *Jatra* to give way to British theatre which became *our own* form of entertainment and education. Thereby *Jatra* has been living in the fringes of our social periphery with an identity of being a matter of ‘gross rural entertainment’.

Fig. 2. Chitpur Jatra para in Kolkata (Source: Author)

Post-Independence *Jatra*

In the post-independence scenario, the culture of rural Bengal witnessed a sea change; media, music, liberalization, westernization influenced the popular rural socio-political and cultural behaviourism very profoundly. Along with this changing panorama *Jatra* slowly shifted from its traditional performative pattern to fit into the popular taste. Now in the mosaic of the several cultural confluences, *Jatra* operates in terms of thematic pattern, songs compositions, dialogic structure, organizational approach, political aim.

In terms of thematic demarcation *Jatra pala* got categorized into social (*Samajik Pala*), historical (*Otihasik Pala*), and mythical (*Puranic Pala*) and came into the public discretion for the first time in 1940's. The cultural taste of rural Bengal in the first few decades of second half of 20th century was captured by the jatrwright (*palakaar*) like Brajen De, Phanibhushan Bidyabinod, Utpal Dutt, Sombhu Bag, Bhairab Ganguly, etc.

Phanibhushan Bidyabinod was not only a great artist but he also wrote *Jatra* like *Mayer Desh*, *Ramanuj*, *Rup Sadhana* or *Sapurer Meye* which aimed at educating the mass regarding the moral values, secularism and nationalism.

Due to the wave of communism in 1960's-70's, *Jatra* became a powerful instrument to mobilize the political participation among the rural Bengali people. Utpal Dutt (1929–1993), Sombhu Bag (1936–2002), Sourindra Mohan Chattopadhyaya (1900 – 1998) tried to wake the mass from their political hibernation. Among all of them, Sombhu Bag was the flag bearer; he wrote *Hitler* (1967) *Ghum Bangar Gan* (1967) *Raktakta Africa* (1971) *Lenin* (1969) *Dak Diye Jai* (1972). His choice of theme suggests that he mainly tried to inform the mass about the political struggle of common people. Sourindra Mohan Chattopadhyaya brought the social consciousness in this traditional art form. In 1970's Bhairab Ganguly, Satya Prakash Dutta, Sailesh Guha Neogi set to the stage. Among them, Bhairab Ganguly (1934–1998) contributed much towards the liberalization of themes of *Jatra*. His early operas like *Rakte Ranga Dhan* (1963), *Ek Paysa* (1967), *Ma Mati Manus* (1974) *Barna Parichay* (1975) *Achal Paysa* (1977), *Ghum Nei* (1978) contained a voice of revolutionary spirit in accordance with Marxist view of socio-political oppression.

Political *Jatra* of Bag, Dutt and Chattopadhyay were the instrument of changing political consciousness among the mass in West Bengal and ultimately paved the way for Communist Party of India to gain power in 1977. Recently the right-wing politics uses *Jatra* too. In 2011, West Bengal experienced the rise of Mamata Banerjee in power overthrowing the long regime of the Left Party. Her political struggle from her movement at Hazra Crossing to Singur and Nadigram is faithfully obliged in the recent operas like *Banglar Khomotay Ebar Mamata* (2011) and *Ekaler Durga* (2012). Thus, for both political wing – the Left and Right, *Jatra* has been a powerful medium to reach the rural mass in Bengal.

During the last decades of the 20th century, producers began to control *Jatra*; they represent and even sometimes create the 'culture' of the rural Bengal. Bhairab Ganguly's later *Jatra Gandhari Janani* (1983), *Bhagaban Babu* (1984), *Koli Yuger Bou* (1985), *Thanay Jachhe Chhoto Bou* (1992) followed populist ideologies because of the choice of the spicy theme, use of colloquial language and proverbs. Bhairab Ganguly set the tune for the populist *Jatra* which aimed to reap commercial benefit for the producers, actors and organizers. In the meantime, the rural Bengali imagination got the taste of silver screen; the legendary Bengali actor Uttam Kumar began to mesmerize the audience with his elegant grace and presence and *Jatrawrights* begin to imitate his hit numbers. Swapan Kumar took all the popular cinema of Uttam Kumar on the *Jatra* stage. He staged *Saptapadi*, (adapted by Biru Mukhopadhyaya) *Sanyasi Raja* (adapted by Satya Pakash Dutta) *Stree* (by Kunal Mukhapadhay), etc.

Nowadays, story of popular Bengali movies and tele-serials are enacted on the open stage of *Jatra*. Also, in terms of stylization of 70's and 80's *Jatra*, the traditional lyrical dialogue was replaced by local dialect; the number of songs reduced, and electric lights replaced the kerosene lights. Organizers began to levy entry fees ranging from rupees 50/- to 200/- per entry for the audience, and *Jatra* became a rural 'entertainment industry'. Then in 1990s, several TV and cinema artists from Tollywood and Bollywood took their entries in *Jatra*. The intrusion of the Tollywood actors created a brand value and hierarchy among

the Banner (producing agency) namely Mega Star, Super Star and Star. Original *Jatra* actors are marginalized by the organizers because these Tollywood actors are considered as the crowd puller. The theme, plot, message, organizers are now being sidelined by the actors and their star value. Usually, the local clubs organize *Jatra* in their areas and spend around 25 thousand to 5 lacs per show depending on the star value of the banner. Along with the change of organizational approach, the modern electronic gadgets like tape recorder, stereophonic sound, western dance troop now accompany this once folk form.

Chitpur Jatra Posters of 2019

Fig. 3. Jatra Posters in 2018-19 (Source: Author)

The Electronic Era in *Jatra*

The *Jatra* world faced a harrowing competition in terms with the newly introduced electronic arrangements in the 1970s. Visual arrangements with electric lights, microphones, projectors (that mostly had to be imported), movable stage, dynamo, etc. not

only raised the cost of the productions but also met out an immense expectation among the mass. Purnendushekhari Bandopadhyay (1911-2008) used lights experimentally in his pala *Swami Vivekananda* (1966) for the first time—calling this phenomenon *Jatrascope*. This new electronic integration created history in *Jatra* world. Breaking through the barriers of stage and reach the mass, he placed several performers among the audience. Microphones were brought into the *Jatra* by the actor Swapan Kumar (1930-2004) in the pala *Michael Madhusudan* (1967). The key reason had been the initiation of women artists for the women roles in *Jatra*. These artists lacked the high tempo and resonating voices that the previous male performers (playing female roles) had. Microphones had thus become indispensable to reach a large number of audiences in an open field.

Using technology was thereby taken to heights by the notable theatre enthusiast Amar Ghosh (4 April 1928 - 3 January 2014) in the production of Shambhu Bag's *Hitler* (1968). In an open arena of *Jatra*, props like rostrum, blocking, wooden slops, twin/multiple exits, unconventional stagecraft, pre-recorded music, etc. were introduced for the first time in the history of *Jatra*. It was made possible by a phenomenal *Jatra*-actor-producer Shantigopal (aka Birendra Narayan Paul, 4 August 1934- 5 November 2012) who brought a revolution in *Jatra* in terms of themes and forms. Along with his teacher-friend Amar Ghosh he brought in several meaningful and successful productions like *Lenin*, *Raja Rammohan*, *Napoleon*, *Ramala Circus*, *Ami Subhas*, etc. Among the performers and audience, not all had welcomed the electronic acrobats in *Jatra* for a long time. While no group was getting a show without the myriad lights and microphones, Calcutta's Natta Company still held to their old customs and put up a resistance to the electronic mumbo-jumbo.

Due to the hurling popularity of *Nati Binodini* (1973), Natta Company had to bring in microphones for the first time. Almost a decade later, Natta Company brought artist Tapas Sen and his lighting directions in their new pala, namely *Kagajer Ful* and *Kuberer Pasha*; the visual effects reached its zenith with their next production *Gangaputra Bhisma*. Nevertheless, the subsequent production *Kurukshetre Krishna* tolled the impending dooms' day of Natta Company in particular, and to the electronic stunts in general. This costly production had exceeded all standards of *Jatra* convention with a projector machine that ensembled the stage and some pre-recorded footage. Unlike the closed space in theatre halls, the open arena did not quite do justice to these lighting and projection. Neither the *Jatra* audience did not welcome cinematic efficacies in watching a *Jatra* performance. To this misfortune, Natta Company's Makhanlal Natta sadly commented, "The *Jatra* audience are susceptible. If they reject anything, they do it from the core of their hearts—never to take it back. If they like something—even trash—their hearts cannot be changed anymore" (Das, 29).

Not only the audience but many veteran *Jatra* artists like Panchu Sen, Fanibhushan Vidyavinod, Brajen De showed their disapproval to this unnecessary electronic paraphernalia in a rustic performative tradition like *Jatra*. They warned that the innocence of the interactive art-form in *Jatra* would succumb to doom in no time. Moreover, that the didactic sublimity that was engrained in *Jatra* would soon be lost in such cinematic effects and momentary splendour. This obvious predicament of *Jatra* saw its release in the 1990s and the early 2000, when a magic show or a jugglery circus had to be performed either before or after the enactment to pull a crowd.

Commercialization & Jatra

Since the 1960s, *Jatra* found a reworking into a professional-commercial-economic venture, following its sociological conditions. The Metropolis of Calcutta, suburban towns and the rural areas formed a core-periphery economic-sociological and cultural relationship; and an innate demand/imitation for urban culture surfaced out of it. The urban-rural cultural exchange intensified as *Jatra* relocated to north Calcutta at Chitpur, which was the outskirts of the Calcutta theatres and amidst the red-light districts (Dutt & Munsii, 124). During this time, a term that found a place in the *Jatra* world is *Gadi*. It heralded a commercial wage-labour element in *Jatra* for the first time. The concept of *Gadi* (transaction offices) came from the Marwari business community, who gradually became the owners and investors of the *Jatra* troupes. A complete professional set up started to operate within *Jatra* and wages and salary could now be negotiated according to popularity 'box-office appeal'.

The 1970s saw an upsurge in terms of competitive *Jatra* groups and cinemas. Popularity became equivalent to monetary profits, while success to particular *pala* relied solely upon the reactionary audience earlier. *Jatra* got caught in between the consumerist culture and aesthetic grounding. *Jatra* which had been the sole entertaining medium till now, saw a rapid downfall in economic profits, thematic diversity, etc. *Jatra* world started to follow the theatre acumens blindly. Stage, compositions, lights, blocks, props, rostrum, etc. found a rampant way to *Jatra* in this phase.

Fig. 4. Jatra-posters' exhibit at Paschimbanga Jatra Academy (Source: Author)

Soon advertising became an integral part in *Jatra* productions. On the day of Rathyatra every year, new *pala* are advertised with remarkable surprises. Some promise glamorous stars from the cinema or theatres, some promise cabaret dancers — a fashion following contemporary films. Some would bring in circus animals, while others would promise to show puppetry or magic shows. Once such a *pala* advertised to an extent where the Director (Master) promised to “cut a woman into two pieces before the *Jatra*

performance begins” (Das 336). Inevitably it reminds us of famous and contemporary magicians like P.C Sircar who indeed performed such magic-tricks on the stage.

Entertainment in the agrarian belt, despite the easy accessibility to television soaps and serials, has not diminished the charm and attraction of the *Jatra* performance. As a recent newspaper report also highlighted, even urban people are gathering in large numbers to see *Jatras* as the 12th *Jatra* Festival held in Kolkata. Though we have women replicating the gyrating dancers of Bollywood culture even in a down-to-earth social drama set in Bengal, the thrust area of each tale will revolve around a stereotypical Bengali woman, both critiquing and entertaining us. *Jatra* is alive and thriving in its own popularity and it would be wrong to consider it as a devalued cultural form, inferior in taste. It is part of the socially accepted forms of normative behaviour, and as the popularity charts and ratings prove, it is still the best medium to voice contemporary social issues. The posters and signboards of the *Jatra* offices are often advertisements of women—being targeted as “the ones who inhabit the place for pleasure and gratification as well as for business” (Dutt & Munsii, 133).

The Popularity Quotient

Popular culture and mass mobilization are the two major factors that gave a shift on a broader acceptance and tolerance level in the mediocre morality in Bengal. The make-believe family drama, gestural make-over and artist's imperfections are widely accommodated within the performative framework. Earlier the viewers have been the greatest critics of *Jatra*. Earlier, till the 1970s, there would be five to six nights of *Jatragaan* at one place. If a day's performance would not go well, the actors could not go outside their rooms; the mass would catcall them down.

In post-independence Bengal, the proscenium staging convention built a gap between the artists and the audience. The actors and the character were unanimous for the audience in the Theatre, while, the *Jatra Asar* (arena) would permit communication between the audience and actors. The *Jatra* actor would sit among the audience asking for a *biri* (local cigarette) with his makeup on, “taking the audience into confidence” (*Jatra Academy Patrika* 5th Vol., 135). The imaginative audience would find this natural, taking the actor as a common man, while he is not performing.

Fig. 5. *Jatradal of Nandakumar, 2020 (Source: Author)*

Abanindranath Tagore tried to differentiate these two forms—theatre and *Jatra* on several paradigms:

Jatra is something, Theatre is something else, and *Jatra*-deformed-modern Theatre-*Jatra* is another thing. The first one is real homemade stuff, the second is an imported foreign good, and theatre-*Jatra* is as seemingly homegrown as the swadeshi-cigarette. The purest *Jatra* is extinct. What we find today is Theatre-*Jatra*; That is why it is hard to imagine the ideal form of *Jatra* and impossible to talk about it (1).

Tagore's argument over the theatrical *Jatra* falls in place with its sustainability and ever-continuing popularity. At different points of time, *Jatra* has catered the need of the hour in building a social consciousness in post-independence Bengal; sometimes in capacity building among the youth in communal harmony and sometimes in empowering the downtrodden classes. It has also advocated the empowerment of women, spoke against bride burning or dowry issues and has actively tried to wake the mass from their political hibernation. Moreover, its impact on the grass root levels of the society is magnanimous and has been growing since ever.

A massive publicity campaign around the *Jatra* with the leading groups got launched in the 1970s. During this phase, salary scales of the artists, large advertising budget, large performing arena indicated that the *Jatra* was manoeuvring as the dominant cultural industry in West Bengal. The three-decade-long migration in Bengal brought a marked shift in the public and private lives of the actresses (both male and female) along with the inherent sociological transformation in both rural and urban population of West Bengal.

Jatra's sojourn into popular culture has proved detrimental to its innate identity. Although it fathoms on a cultural nostalgia in contemporary Bengal, it acts as a powerful tool in rural development and mass mobilization. Capital investment and profit motives were directly proportional to the audience's interest. Bollywood Stars were brought in *Jatra* with a lucrative remuneration (Raveena Tandon acted in a *Jatra* group that charged 3.5 Lakh rupees per show). Tollywood Star cast *Jatra* charges around 1.75 - 3 Lakh rupees/per show. Although, renowned *Jatra* artists have less - earning, but steady *Jatra* shows: Piyali Basu earns rupees 20,000/show, Mitali Chakraborty 13,000/show, Samata Das earns 10,000/night. Below is a chart showing the performance slab according to the remuneration in INR currency per show (single show in a single night).

Fig. 6. Star-casting Banners in present-day *Jatra* (Source: Author)

Conclusion

Despite every impediment, *Jatra* has been adjusting with cultural transformation over the last seventy years. Also, it assimilates society and culture in the rural areas of Bengal till date. Modern-day digitalization includes a study in several mediums where *Jatra* is talked about, performed, taken together. The usage of pre-recorded video footage, computer graphics, audio jingles have replaced the traditional technicians but found to be amply used on digital platforms like YouTube. Earlier, even if people did like some productions, there was a rare chance to watch it again. Archiving the videos of *Jatra* cater to such needs, gauge the present scenario and widen the viewership all around the world. As a popular source of entertainment in rural Bengal, *Jatra* is a powerful medium to reach the mass directly.

In the mosaic of the several cultural confluences, the thematic pattern, lights, musical compositions, dialogue structure, organizational approach, political aim and (re)presenting woman on the stage have changed so much that the performative circumstances of *Jatra* operas have become a new hybrid genre where there are no sharp cultural and conceptual frontiers between tradition and modernity, low and high culture, rural and urban, art and industry and entertainment and education. The critical changes in *Jatra* occurred in its thematic, performative and presentational stances. To gauge the new-age transformation, it is crucial to study the rapid change in socio-economic circumstances and the effects of Consumerism and Digitalization.

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